

Fostering F.A.I.R. Data and Standards in Rare Hematological Diseases

Deliverable 3.1

Website and social media channels

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Disclaimer

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Table of Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
CING	The Cyprus Institute of Neurology and Genetics
ECRs	Early-career researchers
EU	European Commission
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
RD	Rare diseases
RHDs	Rare Haematological diseases
STSE	Short-term staff exchange

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1. Executive Summary

The present deliverable describes the content of the sections included in the HemaFAIR project website and how these sections will be populated as the project progresses. The project website (www.hemafairproject.eu) contains public information about the HemaFAIR project. Briefly, it introduces the general aim and objectives of the project, the partner institutions involved and their roles, information on proposed training activities, all resources related to the project, and announcements about the activities that will take place throughout the project.

Additionally, the social media channels (Facebook, LinkedIn, YouTube, Twitter, Instagram) set up for the projects are also presented in this deliverable. For convenience, the table below lists the links to all the social media channels for the HemaFAIR project.

Social Media Channel	Link
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=61562913125244&sk=about
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/hemafair/?viewAsMember=true
YouTube	http://www.youtube.com/@HemaFAIR
Twitter	https://x.com/HemaFAIRproject
Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/hemafair/

2. HemaFAIR Website: Introduction

As part of the initial activities of the Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication plan, HemaFAIR has implemented a project website. A choice was made for hemafairproject.eu domain between different domain options.

The project website and social media channels will be used as the main portal to communicate and disseminate all project deliverables and the training activities organised throughout the project. During the earlier phases of the project, the website will introduce the project overview, a brief summary of the idea of FAIR principles, main project contact points, members of the project, and a descriptive summary of activities of each partner institute, and the concepts of the proposed training activities.

As the project gets more mature and training activities and other networking events are organised, the website will be the main portal for announcements of these activities. All resources related to HemaFAIR such as publications, media (press releases, interviews, etc), newsletters, or training materials (slide decks, videos, posters, abstracts, etc.) will be publicly available and presented on the project website.

The navigation within the website is straightforward with pages accessible from the home page and subpages. At the current stage of the project, the website is launched with a simple structure, and it will be populated and updated further as more content is generated by the project.

The present document introduces the main structure and features of the HemaFAIR website and provides a brief overview of the social media channels.

3. Website structure

The navigation bar to go to different pages is horizontally located at the top right. Horizontal navigation bars are easier for people to navigate once they stay on the website and discover the content in more detail.

Figure 1 HemaFAIR website structure diagram

3.1 HOME

This section is designed to summarise the main top-point information on the HemaFAIR project to the visitor in a concise way. Sub-sections included in the HOME section are summarised below;

Figure 2 Home page

- **Project mission:** As a one-sentence summary of the HemaFAIR project aims. This provides visitors with a clear and immediate understanding of the HemaFAIR purpose and goals, helping to establish a connection and set the tone for the entire user experience.

Figure 3 Project mission

- **Upcoming events:** To be populated with the events organised throughout the project. This will inform the visitors about important dates and opportunities to engage with the project.

Figure 4 Upcoming events

- **Most recent news:** To be populated with a summary of recent news throughout the project. This is to ensure that visitors are up-to-date with the latest developments and updates.

Figure 5 Most recent news

- **Contact Us banner:** This information is provided on the HOME page to make it easy for visitors to connect, seek support, or provide feedback, to enhance user engagement.

Figure 6 Contact Us banner

3.2 ABOUT HemaFAIR

After a general overview in the HOME section, in the next section, more detailed information on HemaFAIR aims and objectives is implemented in the 'About HemaFAIR' section. This section is separated from the 'HOME' section to keep the website content as simple and light as possible throughout each tab and to avoid overwhelming the visitor with lots of information at once. In this way, the visitors will reach more detailed information as they wish if they navigate through the next sections. Sub-sections included in 'About HemaFAIR' are summarised below:

- **HemaFAIR:** To provide a more extensive overview of the project and its dissemination materials, summarising the main topics that will be focussed on the project such as training programme, FAIRification of research data, ethics, and

regulatory issues. By highlighting these topics, the aim is to introduce the visitor to the idea of how they can connect with the project in their topic of interest.

Figure 7 HemaFAIR page banner

- **Objectives:** To highlight the specific project objectives and clarify the project's aims and intended outcomes, guiding users through the purpose-driven aspects of the project. This section also summarises the information on the funding call.

Figure 8 Objectives page banner

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Figure 9 Objectives page

- **FAIR principles:** As the main objectives of HemaFAIR are to implement FAIR principles to research data, and to improve the knowledge of FAIR principles, this section is implemented to provide a more detailed overview of what these principles are. This section aims to set the tone of the project aims, which are specifically on FAIR principles, and provide an overview of these principles to the visitors concisely.

Figure 10 FAIR principles banner

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Figure 11 FAIR principles

- **Members:** This will feature the members of the project and will introduce the team behind the work, personalizing the project and highlighting the expertise and diverse skills of each partner.

Figure 12 Members' banner

Figure 13 Example screenshot from the members' page

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3.3 NEWS/EVENTS

This section will include information on the project activities in the form of different materials such as press releases related to project achievements, training activities organised, the announcement of new project publications, attendance to conferences or other events, etc.

It will be updated often with new information to keep the audience up-to-date on the project's progress. The Coordinating partner (CING) is responsible for updating the content of the website.

HemaFAIR training activities such as workshops, webinars, and transferable skill lecture series will be announced here for the visitors to express interest in attendance.

Figure 14 News banner

Figure 15 Events banner

3.4 TRAINING ACTIVITIES

The establishment of a training programme is one of the main objectives of the HemaFAIR project. The training programme will include different communication and dissemination activities such as short-term staff exchanges, summer schools, workshops, webinars, expert visits, lecture series, and mentoring programmes. These activities are separated into different tabs and a short description for each of them is provided in their corresponding tab. If a training activity involves attendance from different groups within CING or other institutions in Cyprus (Summer schools, workshops, webinars, lecture series, mentoring programme) an 'express interest' tab is also provided in this section.

Figure 16 Short-term staff exchanges banner

Figure 17 Short-term staff exchanges page

Figure 18 Summer Schools banner

Figure 19 Summer Schools page

Figure 20 Workshop page banner

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Specific hands-on workshops are organised for Cypriot stakeholders in research and innovation management and support as well as scientific topics related to FAIR principles and RHDs. If you would like to express interest, please contact us on info@hemafairproject.eu.

Figure 21 Workshops page

Figure 22 Webinars page banner

Webinars related to issues of research and innovation management and support are organized twice per year. These webinars are targeted for research and innovation managers, administrators, ECRs, experienced researchers. If you would like to express interest, please contact us on info@hemafairproject.eu.

Figure 23 Webinars page

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Figure 24 Expert visits page banner

Figure 25 Expert visits page

Figure 26 Lecture series page banner

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Figure 27 Lecture series page

Figure 28 Mentoring programme page banner

Figure 29 Mentoring programme page

Figure 30 Express interest page banner

A form for the 'Express interest' page. At the top, it asks 'How to participate?' and explains that users should fill in the form to be contacted. The form includes several input fields: 'Your Name', 'Your Surname', 'Affiliation', 'Your Email', and 'Mobile Number'. Below these are checkboxes for 'Lectures', 'Summer Schools', 'Workshops', 'Mentorship Programmes', 'Webinars', and 'Expert Visits'. A 'Message' text area is at the bottom, followed by a blue 'Send' button.

Figure 31 Express interest page

3.5 RESOURCES

In this section scientific publications related to HemaFAIR, digital resources, newsletters released and all the content of training materials (leaflets, brochures, lecture slides) will be made publicly available. Each of these (publications, media, newsletters, training material) is designed to be in a separate tab on the project website.

Figure 32 Publications page banner

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Figure 33 Media page banner

Figure 34 Newsletter page banner

Figure 35 Training material page banner

3.6. CONTACT US

This section is implemented for visitors to reach out to us for any questions, feedback, or enquiries related to HemaFAIR. It is meant to be as straightforward as possible and to facilitate contact with the Coordinating beneficiary (CING). For this reason, a simple form is created and the contact information of the Coordinator is also provided.

For any questions about HemaFAIR, do not hesitate to reach out by filling the form or using the contact details below

Your Name Your Email

Message

[Send](#)

Contact info
 Petros Kountouris
 Project Coordinator
 petrosk@cing.ac.cy

Figure 36 Contact info page

3.7 FOOTER

The footer of the website contains quickly accessible links to social media channels of the project, newsletter subscription, and privacy policy. Along with the European Union emblem, the HemaFAIR logo is designed and implemented with the FAIR principles concept (the symbols of magnifying glass for 'findable', key for 'accessible', reusability arrow for 'reusable' and network symbol for 'interoperability').

Subscribe to our newsletter
 to keep you up to date on our activities.

Email

I agree to receive the newsletter and know that I can easily unsubscribe at any time.

[Subscribe](#)

HemaFAIR

[f](#) [@](#) [x](#) [v](#) [in](#)

Contact Us
 info@hemafairproject.eu

Features
[Home](#)
[HemaFAIR](#)
[Privacy Policy](#)

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Figure 37 Website footer

4. Social Media Channels

Social media are essential tools for communication and dissemination and they cover a strategic importance in the Dissemination and Communication plans. These channels will be regularly used for news information and general outreach, and they will refer to the website as much as possible to boost the clicks of the visitors.

These social media channels will be implemented in the project website footer for quick access. The links to the social media channels are summarised in the table below.

Social Media Channel	Link
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=61562913125244&sk=about
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/hemafair/?viewAsMember=true
YouTube	http://www.youtube.com/@HemaFAIR
Twitter	https://x.com/HemaFAIRproject
Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/hemafair/

Figure 38 HemaFAIR LinkedIn page

For LinkedIn (as well as Facebook and Instagram) the first post was a repost from the Cyprus Institute of Neurology & Genetics (CING) LinkedIn page regarding the kick-off meeting that took place on 11-12 July 2024. Sharing the post via CING's main LinkedIn page which has

over 5000 followers gave the HemaFAIR project good visibility on LinkedIn. Project partners (other than CING) also reposted this post which further helped with reaching more audiences. As the project matures, further updates will be made available on the LinkedIn page.

Figure 39 First post on the kick-off meeting

An introductory video on HemaFAIR project was also posted on HemaFAIR social media channels (Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn, Facebook) summarising the FAIR principles and introducing the audience to different types of training activities which will be organised as part of the project.

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Figure 40 HemaFAIR introductory video

Figure 41 HemaFAIR Facebook Page

Figure 42 HemaFAIR Instagram Page

Figure 43 HemaFAIR Twitter Page

Figure 44 HemaFAIR Youtube Channel